

An underwater scene with a network overlay. The background is a deep blue ocean with light rays filtering through the water. A white network of lines and dots is overlaid on the right side of the image, extending from the top right towards the bottom right.

Tracking the Pulse of the Ocean

Website

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Comments:	<p>The website was accessible on 28 November 2025, under the domain biogeosea.eu, but was still protected by a password that only allowed the project consortium to access it. Due to the delayed approval of the data protection information by the GEOMAR data protection officer and the final migration to the GEOMAR servers, the website was only publicly accessible from 15 December 2025 onwards.</p> <p>All work package leaders and co-leaders provided content for the website.</p>

Project information	
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Project acronym	BioGeoSea
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Project website	https://biogeosea.eu

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents a short accompanying document to the BioGeoSea project website, which can be accessed at <https://biogeosea.eu> and serves as the central platform for communication and dissemination throughout the project's lifetime. The website provides accessible information on project objectives, structure, expected key exploitable results, and scientific context, along with regularly updated news and events. A comprehensive library section makes public deliverables, publications, policy briefs, and communication materials freely available. The website was commissioned by GEOMAR and developed by schweitzer media gmbh, then migrated to and hosted on GEOMAR servers. GEOMAR maintains and curates the site, ensuring a secure, compliant, and high-quality public interface for the project.

2 Introduction

This deliverable describes the official website of the BioGeoSea project, created to support its communication and dissemination obligations under Horizon Europe. As a publicly accessible portal, the website provides essential information about the project's objectives, progress, and outputs, ensuring transparency and supporting engagement with scientific communities, policymakers, stakeholders, and the wider public.

3 Website Purpose and Scope

The BioGeoSea website is the project's central public communication platform. It offers clear information about the project's goals, structure, partners, achievements, and scientific foundations. In addition, several dedicated sections support the ongoing dissemination of project activities and results.

Key components of the website include:

- General project information, providing accessible descriptions of the project approach and challenges addressed by BioGeoSea including:
 - Mission & vision statement
 - Key objectives
 - Key Exploitable Results
- Project structure, providing a good overview of work packages and tasks
- News and Events pages providing timely updates on project progress, meetings, outreach activities, and relevant community events
- A comprehensive library section, serving as the repository for all publicly available project outputs, including:
 - Public deliverables
 - Policy briefs and specific reports
 - Scientific publications
 - Communication materials such as the project logo, roll-up, and overview poster

- A Knowledge Hub as a dedicated section designed to provide concise, accessible insights for the scientific community and other key stakeholders:
 - Offering a high-level overview of the four phenomena analysed in the project and explaining their links to biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).
 - Conceived as a living section that will expand over time as the project progresses.
 - Future content will highlight key developments, such as advances in indicator development and other major project achievements.
 - All contributions are intentionally short, precise, and easy to digest, serving as an alternative to lengthy reports while still conveying scientifically relevant results.

These features ensure that BioGeoSea's progress, outputs, and key findings are openly accessible to all interested audiences.

4 Development, Hosting, and Maintenance

In October, GEOMAR commissioned the schweitzer media gmbh - already responsible for other project communications - to build the new project website (<https://biogeosea.eu>). At the outset, the project coordination held several short meetings with the contractor to define requirements and site structure. The main criteria agreed upon were: (1) rapid loading even under low-bandwidth conditions (e.g. in remote areas or on ships); (2) a simple content management system allowing the project manager to independently post news items; and (3) the ability to make minor edits without outside support.

Based on these criteria and the target audience - potential stakeholders such as interested maritime-industry partners, policymakers, and scientists - the website's structure was designed to be clear and functional to ensure that visitors quickly find essential information, stay updated, and can easily get in contact with the project coordination if they wish to engage.

After completion and testing, the website was migrated from the contractor's server to GEOMAR's servers, where it will be hosted, maintained, and curated for the full duration of the project and beyond.

The development and migration process required close coordination with:

- GEOMAR's Data Protection Officer, ensuring full GDPR compliance,
- GEOMAR's IT team, responsible for secure hosting, technical setup, and long-term operational stability, and
- GEOMAR's media and communications team, ensuring alignment with institutional communication practices, accessibility requirements, and branding guidelines.

This collaborative approach ensures that the website is secure, sustainable, professionally presented, and compliant with all relevant institutional and European standards.

5 Communication Channels Linked to the Website

To increase visibility and broaden outreach, the BioGeoSea website is complemented by an official social media presence: LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/biogeosea/>

This platform is used to amplify website content, share news and events, promote publications, and engage stakeholders across the marine science and industry as well as environmental policy communities.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable document summarizes the establishment of BioGeoSea's primary online communication platform. The website provides a stable, accessible, and well-maintained hub for disseminating project information and results. With continuous updates supported by GEOMAR's hosting and curation, it ensures transparency, supports stakeholder engagement, and contributes to the project's long-term communication and dissemination objectives.